

ELEMENTS OF CULTIVATION TECHNOLOGY AND FEATURES OF PEANUTS CULTURE IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract The article presents agrotechnical information about the valuable oilseed crop peanuts. Statistical data on the area and technology of cultivation of zoned varieties of this crop in the Republic of Uzbekistan are presented. The need for the production of various oilseeds, including peanuts, which are valuable raw materials for the confectionery, medical and technical industries, is substantiated. Agrotechnical requirements for sowing peanuts are described. The technical characteristics of pneumatic precision planters used in agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan are given.

At the present stage of development of agricultural production, one of the main tasks of the agricultural policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the need to produce various oilseed agricultural crop, including peanuts, which are valuable raw materials for the confectionery, medical and technical industries. Peanuts (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) are a type of annual legume that originated in South America. More than 100 countries in the world grow peanuts over large areas, with an average yield of 1.3 t/ha. Peanuts contain 45-50% oil and 30% protein, and are a rich source of minerals (Ca, Mg, P, K, Fe) and vitamins [1]. About two-thirds of the world's peanut production is used for oil production. The remaining third is used as a final food product. In Uzbekistan, peanuts occupy about seven thousand hectares. The Uzbek Crop Research Institute (UzNIIR) is studying peanut samples from the International Crop Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics (ICRISAT). From 28 studied samples of ICRISAT peanuts, samples of early ripening peanuts with high yields and large seeds were isolated. As a result of the study, two varieties of peanuts were released: “Salomat” and “Mumtoz”, which occupy significant areas in Uzbekistan. The Mumtoz variety is released for main sowing, and the Salomat variety is released for both main and re-sowing in the south of Uzbekistan (Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions).

Currently, the “Tashkent-112” variety, belonging to the Valencia group, and the “Kibray-4” peanut variety, belonging to the Virginia group, are cultivated in Uzbekistan. Both varieties were created at UzNIIR. The peanut variety “Kibray-4” was released in 2000 and is high-yielding (3-3.4 t/ha) and large-seeded (the weight of 100 seeds is 80 g), but due to the pink color of the seeds and the hard shell of the bean, this variety has not a great success. The peanut variety “Tashkent-112” is mid-season,

medium-yielding, small- and red-seeded. This variety is very widespread and has great demand in the market.

In addition more than 20 different varieties of organic peanuts are grown in Uzbekistan. More nutritious organic peanuts contain more vitamins, minerals and antioxidants than traditional peanuts. Some of the most popular varieties include “Shirgala” peanuts, which are known for their rich flavor, and “Andijon” peanuts, which are famous for their high protein content.

According to data given in sources [3], farmers in Uzbekistan annually export over 6.100 tons of peanuts to Russia. According to the UN Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), Uzbek farmers grow about 7.500 thousand tons of peanuts annually. The soil and climatic conditions of Uzbekistan make it possible to grow peanuts in almost all areas with a yield of 27...30 c/ha.

One of the main ways to obtain a high yield is the method of planting and the technology of its implementation. Currently, in world practice, the creation of seeding aggregates with high productivity and adapted to specific soil and climatic conditions is carried out in two directions: increasing the level of versatility of planters and the use of centralized reservoirs for seeds. However, the existing models of planters do not fully meet the agrotechnical requirements for uniform sowing of seeds and at the same time lead to high costs. In this regard, it is very important to evaluate the model of the sowing apparatus with high accuracy, adapted to certain soil and climatic conditions of Uzbekistan.

The sowing scheme should provide a nutritional area in rainfed conditions - $70 \times (25-30)$ cm, in irrigated conditions - $70 \times (10-15)$ cm. In continuous plantings, the distance between bunch-type plants can be 30×60 cm or 15×75 cm; for shoot types, more space is allowed [2].

Peanuts are often sown together with other species. The most common sowing method is wide-row with row spacing of 70 cm. For this, corn or cotton planters are used. Peanuts can be cultivated using the checkrow pocket method according to a 70×70 cm pattern with 6-8 plants in one checkrow pocket [4]. This method has the advantage of increasing productivity and reducing labor costs for caring for crops by 1.5-2.0 times.

The sowing rate of husked seeds is 50-80 kg/ha. The rate is increased by 25% when sowing whole or broken beans. The optimal plant density is 100-120 thousand/ha. The sowing depth is 6-8 cm and depends on the moisture content and granulometric composition of the soil. Technical characteristics of pneumatic seeders used today in the fields of our Republic according to specific standards is given in the table.

Planter brand	Working width, m	Operating speed, km/soat	Seeding rate, pieces/m	Seeding disc parameters	
				diameter, mm	number of cells, pieces
SPC6M (Romania)	2,7-4,8	5,5-8,8	7 - 40	140	6-40
CMX-4-04-01 (Uzbekistan)	2,4/2,8/3,6	7,2	11 - 30	153	24
PPAES-4 (Uzbekistan)	3,6	7,42	7,2 - 35	220	48
Case1200 (USA)	7,2	6,8-12,8	4,6 - 26	295	24-130
Sönmezler (Turkey)	3,6	6,0-8,7	1,5 - 50	230	8-64
Monosem (France)	5,4	7,0-8,0	5,5 - 17	240	36
TC-M 4150 (Russia)	3,6	8,08	11 - 27	241	72
Planter 3M (France)	2,8-3,6	6,0-8,7	7,4-22,2	220	48

Caring for crops. After sowing, it is recommended to roll the soil. Caring for crops comes down to maintaining the soil in a loose, weed-free state. It consists in: pre-emergence harrowing; 3-5 inter-row cultivations to a depth of 6 to 8 (10) cm with weeding of the rows; 1-2 hillings during flowering and appearance (burrowing) of gynophores.

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